

MARITAL ADJUSTMENT: COMPARISON BETWEEN WORKING AND NON- WORKING WOMEN

DR. KALYANI JHA ¹

¹ ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, DEPT. OF PSYCHOLOGY, GRADUATE SCHOOL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, JAMSHEDPUR, KOLHAN UNIVERSITY, CHAIBASA.

ABSTRACT:

The transition to married life signifies a profound transformation, as marriage embodies a way of living rather than merely a relational status. The purpose of this study was to investigate how married women, both those who work and those who do not, adjust to the institution of marriage. A person's choice to commit to another for the rest of their lives is reflected in their marriage. The efficacy of the relationship hinges on the partners' ability to adapt, suggesting that it is not invariably a straightforward or enjoyable endeavor. A significant number of families are facing notable difficulties in terms of adaptation and marital relationships as the occurrence of dual-income households rises. This study focused on the dynamics of marital adjustment, particularly examining the differences between working women and their non-working counterparts. In the sample, half of the women are without employment, while the other half is engaged in work. This study employed a marital adjustment inventory developed by Rohatgi and Kumar in 2018. A statistical examination of the acquired data was conducted utilizing the t-test, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. This analysis involved a thorough examination of the marital adjustment rates among working and nonworking women, utilizing the 't' test for our evaluation. The research indicated that there was no statistically significant disparity between women who are employed and those who are not employed. The research findings highlight the necessity for increased female engagement in the workforce and underscore the significance of males embracing a more supportive and encouraging role as collaborators in the professional environment.

KEYWORDS:

MARITAL ADJUSTMENT, WORKING, ADAPTATION AND NON-WORKING WOMEN.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

19th November 2024

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

20th November 2024

INTRODUCTION

The strength of women has never wavered. In the fight for human dignity, they are constantly in the vanguard. To their male counterpart, they have been a source of strength and encouragement. Women have several hats to wear. Especially after getting married, they take on a lot of responsibilities and manage stress well at home and at work. In India, a marriage brings together not only the spouses but also their families and any other relatives they may have. Typically, it is the family members that make the marriage choice. The two people involved will need to familiarize themselves with one another's customs and practices, adapt to different settings and people, and shoulder the burden of caring for one another and their families. The goal of any marriage is to make the couple happy. An essential part of becoming an adult is making a legally binding commitment, and marriage is no exception. It took maturity and success in life to choose a spouse and commit to a marriage.

Choosing a life partner to be married to is a huge deal. People get married for a variety of reasons, including seeking happiness, friendship, or a way out of a bad circumstance. Adaptation is a key component of a robust

and successful marital life. Life may be much better for individuals who are able to adapt in their married lives compared to others who struggle with this. Every person's wants and worries are met by society via the marriage system, which ensures the life and success of society. This is why marriage is a social security for all people. The joy, contentment, and fulfilment that come from marriage stem from the many benefits it offers, including the opportunity to grow as an individual, connect with others, build trust, gain knowledge, and fulfil societal duties. As a couple grows older, they must go through a process of adjustment that helps them fit to one another's tastes, identify one another's characteristics, establish behavioural standards, and build relationship models.

MARITAL ADJUSTMENT

The ability of a married person to adapt to the dynamics of their marriage is a critical factor in determining how functioning they are as a married person. It is a normal expectation for people to have the hope that their spouses would be able to adjust to the dynamics of their marriage. The process of modernization in a society brings about considerable changes in a variety of aspects, most notably

in the frameworks of its economic and cultural systems. A man's connection with a woman in marriage may be the most profound type of relational engagement since it incorporates not only the physical, emotional, and spiritual aspects of their relationship, but also the social and societal aspects of their relationship. It is intimately connected to the capacity of the pair to work together in a productive manner that the success of a marriage is measured. The degree to which the personalities of the husband and wife are compatible is one of the most important factors that determine the success of marital unions. One of the defining characteristics of a successful marriage is the presence of a marital coalition, which is characterized by the fact that both couples actively address one other's needs and acknowledge the contrasts between their individual experiences and the larger cultural environment. In order for a marriage to be considered "adjusted," it is necessary for both parties to experience a considerable amount of contentment and pleasure within the context of their relationship.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- The quality of a husband and wife's married life is significantly impacted when they are able to make the transition to married life. In many circumstances, marital maladjustment leads to conflict, tensions, and divorce. The marital adjustment of working women and non-working women has been the subject of several research. Working women outperformed stay-at-home mothers in many areas, including self-esteem, life satisfaction, subjective wellbeing, overall health, and marital adjustment (Nathawat and Mathur, 2013).
- As to the findings of Rinku (2013), the level of marital adjustment is greater for women who do not have jobs than it is for women who have jobs. According to the findings of Hashmi et al., married women who are employed have more marital troubles than married women who are not employed.
- Gupta and Nafis (2014) found that women who did not work had a higher rate of success in adjusting to their new marital status compared to women who did work.
- The research conducted by Yadava (2018) aimed to evaluate the extent to which the views of social support held by working and nonworking women impacted their marital adjustment. According to the findings, the level of marital adjustment experienced by working mothers was shown to be higher than that of mothers who did not work. Women's views of social support, especially from members of their own families, had a role in the adjustment process that occurred throughout marriage.
- When Shreelakshmi (2021) conducted a study on the topic of marital adjustment, she contrasted the

experiences of working women and nonworking women. She found that the two groups' experiences were considerably different from one another. According to the findings, working mothers have shown a higher level of marital adjustment compared to nonworking mothers. This major difference between the two groups of mothers is revealed by the findings.

- The research conducted by Tripathi and Kashmiri (2023) aimed to assess the marital adjustment of women in the workforce compared to those who are not employed. A total of sixty women were selected at random from the city of Haldwani, comprising 30 who were employed and 30 who were not employed. The Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (MAQ) was developed and standardized by Dr. Pramod Kumar and Kanchani Rohtagi to assess the level of marital adjustment in both working and non-working women. The t-test, mean, and standard deviation serve as fundamental tools in the realm of statistical analysis. The findings indicate that the marital adjustment of working women is comparable to that of non-working women.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Alongside their paid employment, working women, especially those who are married, face the added responsibility of managing household care for their families. Women in the workforce frequently encounter burnout as they strive to balance their responsibilities both at home and in the workplace. Modern working women often navigate two distinct environments—their professional setting and their home life—leading to a higher prevalence of marital adjustment issues within this group. This research focuses on marital adjustment among working women. When a husband and wife have successfully adapted to their marriage, it indicates a mutual sense of happiness and satisfaction with one another and their overall relationship. Marriage offers a foundation of stability that positively impacts not only the couple but also their children, extended family, and the broader community. A well-adjusted couple can enhance their quality of life, which positively impacts their relationship.

Family and work have consistently been significant concerns for individuals; however, in numerous societies, these challenges have intensified due to societal advancements that have influenced the structures of both work and family. Currently, women are engaged in various sectors, including business, academia, government, nonprofits, and industrial and organizational environments. The ongoing pressures of professional responsibilities and the conflicts that can emerge between family obligations and career commitments render working women particularly vulnerable to challenges in marital adjustment. The current research focuses on marital adjustment among women in Jamshedpur,

comparing those who are employed with those who are not in the workforce.

OBJECTIVE

- ◆ The objective of this research is to examine the marital adjustment levels of employed women and those who are not employed.
- ◆ The objective is to ascertain the differing approaches of employed and unemployed women towards marriage.

HYPOTHESES

- ❖ Marital adjustment level will be equal for working and non-working women.
- ❖ Marital adjustment is similar for working and non-working women.

SAMPLE

The current research was conducted on employed and unemployed women in Jamshedpur. The research included 100 women, consisting of 50 employed and 50 unemployed, aged between 25 and 50 years. Employed women were included among educators, bankers, clerks, etc.

VARIABLES

- ✓ Dependent Variable: *Marital Adjustment*
- ✓ Independent Variable: *Working and Non-Working women*

TOOL

Researchers employed the Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (MAQ) created by Kumar and Rohtagi. In the year (2018). There are a total of 25 yes/no questions on the marital adjustment questionnaire (MAQ), which are categorized into three areas: sexual, social, and emotional. With a dependability of 0.96, it has been widely used in research conducted in India. In this survey, a higher score indicates a more favorable modification, such as Items 9, 20, 23, and 25 are sexual; items 3, 4, 5, 6, 12, 14, 15, and 18, 19 are social; and items 1, 2, 7, 8, 10, 11, 13, 16, 17, 21, 22, and 24 are emotional. Before any individuals filled out the surveys, the researcher gave them an explanation of the study and got their informed permission. A variety of statistical representations, including percentages and proportions, were developed from the investigated data. This scale has a validity rate of 0.84 and a reliability of 0.71. A possible range for the score is 0–25.

DATA ANALYSIS

Percentages were used for data analysis. Results were presented as the mean and standard deviation. To find out if working women and non-working women had significantly different levels of marital adjustment, we employed an independent sample't' test.

RESULT

We measured the frequency of marital adjustment among working women and non-working women by

administering the marital adjustment scale. Based on the scores obtained, three levels of marital adjustment prevalence were categorized: low, moderate, and high.

TABLE-1 LEVEL OF MARITAL ADJUSTMENT AMONG WORKING AND NON WORKING WOMEN

Groups	Poor		Average		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Working Women	10	20	27	54	13	26
Non-Working Women	11	22	27	54	12	24
Total	21	21	54	54	25	25

FIGURE-1 LEVEL OF MARITAL ADJUSTMENT AMONG WORKING AND NON WORKING WOMEN

Women who work and those who do not report varying degrees of marital adjustment was almost same (20% and 22% &26% and 24% respectively).Both groups had comparable levels of average marital adjustment (54% and 54%). Consequently, the hypothesis "Marital adjustment level will be equal for working and non-working women" is affirmed. Among the whole sample, 54% of women exhibited average levels of marital adjustment, 25% shown higher levels, and 21% displayed lower levels.

TABLE-2 COMPARISON BETWEEN WORKING AND NON WORKING WOMEN ON MARITAL ADJUSTMENT

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t value	Level of significance
Working Women	50	24.62	2.73	1.30	Not Significant
Non-Working Women	50	23.91	2.82		

FIGURE-2 MEAN SCORES OF MARITAL ADJUSTMENT AMONG WORKING AND NON WORKING WOMEN

Marital adjustment was not significantly different for working women compared to non-working women, according to the findings. Working women's mean value is 24.62 and non-working women's mean value is 23.91, demonstrating a striking resemblance between the two groups. If the t-value is less than 1.30, it does not indicate statistical significance. Both Aleem et al. (2008) and Jamabo et al. (2012) revealed no significant variations in marital adjustment between working and non-working women. Similarly, there is no difference between women with multiple occupations and those with single careers when it comes to marital adjustment. This study's results are in agreement with those previously reported. Marital adjustment is equally and satisfactorily experienced by working and non-working women, and this is due to factors such as mutual trust, improved understanding, sharing, and respect. Women in the workforce and those who opt to manage their responsibilities at home possess the capability to excel in all areas of domestic life while also attaining success in their careers.

Collaboration between spouses is essential for a successful marriage. Married women tend to flourish when their husbands are supportive, compassionate, and, crucially, take pride in their accomplishments, both professionally and personally. There is no correlation between a woman's family structure and how she adjusts to marriage, whether she works or not. With the help of their in-laws, working women are able to give their whole attention to their jobs and build better bonds with their husbands. Similarly, married women who are not employed can depend on their in-laws for assistance with household responsibilities and childcare, facilitating a smooth transition into married life. Hence the hypothesis "Marital adjustment is similar for working and non-working women" was proved.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings indicate that there was no significant difference in marital adjustment between working women and their non-working counterparts. This indicated that the research hypothesis put forth earlier was indeed accurate. Jamabo et al. (2012) and Aleem et al. (2008) observed no statistically significant difference in marital adjustment between working and non-working women,

thereby reinforcing the validity of these findings. Women in marriage, regardless of their professional engagement, frequently discover that the pillars of mutual understanding, affection, trust, and respect are paramount in fostering a balanced and harmonious relationship. The configuration of familial relationships is a significant factor that can assist married women, regardless of their employment status, in navigating their newly assumed roles with greater efficacy. The transition to married life is likely to be more seamless when in-laws exhibit kindness and offer assistance, particularly in scenarios where they cohabit and contribute to household responsibilities and childcare. Adapting to the nuances of married life presents its own set of challenges. Each married woman, regardless of her employment status, engages in sacrifices for her own happiness and fulfillment; however, these significant alterations may impose challenges on her relationships.

RECOMMENDATION

It is important for women to take the initiative and pursue the occupations that they want. On the other hand, it is possible that working women are able to achieve their objectives as a result of the feelings of fulfilment they have in their marriages and relationships. Additionally, the husband has to alter his attitude; he needs to be supportive of his wife and urge her to concentrate on her professional endeavours.

IMPLICATION

The study's findings are anticipated to be employed by policymakers to enhance their initiatives aimed at empowering women. The findings may provide valuable insights for practitioners aiming to enhance awareness of marital adjustment.

REFERENCES

1. Aleem, Sheema, Danish, Lubna (2008). Marital Satisfaction and Anxiety among Single and Dual Career Women, *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 34, 141- 144.
2. Gupta, A & Nafic, J. (2014) Dose Marital Adjustment and Psychological well-being differ in working and non-working females. *International Journal of Research Engineering & Social Science*, Vol. -4, Issue -3.
3. Jamabo, T., & Ordu, S.N. (2012). Marital adjustment of working class and non-working class women in Port Harcourt metropolis. *International Journal of Psychology and Counseling*. 4(10):123-6.
4. Jamadar, C. (2022). Marital adjustment among degree college professors. *European Journal of Psychological Research*, 9(1), 52-59.
5. Jan, M. (2024). Marital Adjustment among Married Employed and Unemployed Women: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Social Impact*, 9(1), 243-250.

6. M.K., Rema and Kaur, Parneet (2020) "Depression, Anxiety, Stress and Marital Adjustment among Women," *Journal of International Women's Studies*: Vol. 21: Iss. 5.
7. Nathawat, S. S., & Mathur, A. (2013). Marital adjustment and subjective well-being in Indian-educated housewives and working women. *The Journal of psychology*, 127(3), 353-358
8. Paul F. A. (2022). Marital Adjustment among the Employed and Unemployed Women's in the Region of North East: A Cross Sectional Study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 10(2), 183-188.
9. Rajput, N.R. (2017). Marital Adjustment and Happiness, *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Vol. 5(1).
10. Rinku, Rani (2013). Marital adjustment problems of working & non-working women in contrast of their husband. *International journal for research in Education*, 2, 7:40-44.
11. Shreelakshmi, K. (2021). Marital Adjustment among Working and Nonworking Mothers. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(2): 232-238.
12. Sundarraju (2019). Comparison between Working and Non-Working Women On Marital Adjustment And Women Empowerment. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)* Volume 6 Issue 2, February 2019 ISSN: 2394-4404.
13. Yadava, A. (2018). Perceived social support as a determinant of marital adjustment in working and non-working mothers. *IAHRW International Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 6(2), 217-221.